

SHUKUR KHOLMIRZAYEV IS THE CRADLE OF UZBEK PROSE

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Abstract: *This article provides information about the place of the great talent Shukur Kholmirezayev in Uzbek literature, his literary heritage, and the contribution of his works to the development of world thought. The idea and method of expression described in the writer's stories, artistic skills are revealed.*

Key words: *writer, novel, short story, story, autobiography, way of creative development*

SHUKUR XOLMIRZAYEV-O'ZBEK NASRINING DARG'ASI

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada buyuk iste'dod egasi Shukur Xolmirzayevning o'zbek adabiyotida tutgan o'rni, uning adabiy merosi va asarlarining dunyo tafakkuri rivojidagi hissasi haqida ma'lumot beriladi. Adibning hikoyalarda tasvirlangan g'oya va ifoda usuli, badiiy mahorati ochib beriladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *yozuvchi, roman, qissa, hikoya, avtobiografiya, ijodiy takomil yo'li*

Аннотация: *В данной статье представлена информация о роли великого таланта Шукура Холмирзаева в узбекской литературе, его литературном наследии и вкладе его произведений в развитие мировой мысли. Раскрываются идея и способ выражения, описанные в рассказах писателя, его художественное мастерство.*

Ключевые слова: *писатель, роман, рассказ, повесть, автобиография, путь творческого совершенствования.*

Shukur Kholmirezayev, one of the true masters of Uzbek prose of the 20th century, is a writer who has left his name in the world of literature with his talent as high as the mountains of Surkhan land. He was born on March 24, 1940 in Boysun district. He received his secondary education in a district school. A strong passion for science and literature led him to Tashkent, the capital. Young Shukur graduated from the Faculty of Journalism of the Tashkent State University in 1963. He was noticed by great writers as a student with his first works. During his career, he was an

editor at the publishing house "Yosh Gvardiya" (1963-67), a literary fellow at the Musical Drama Theater named after Mukimi (1967-69), at the magazines "Guliston" (1969-75) and "East Star" (1978-80). works as a literary officer, department head. Shukur Kholmirezayev's first stories and essays were published in 1958. Shukur Kholmirezayev, in the early period of his work, used his pen in the short story genre as well as in the genre of "White Horseman" (1962), "Waves" (1963), "Who is not among eighteen?" (1965) creates stories. These works It is one of the best examples of Uzbek short stories of the 60s. The stories written by the writer during this period were later "Under the Distant Stars" (1971), "Life Forever" (1974), "Oghir tash kochsa..." (1980), "Roads, Companions" (1984), "Almond bloomed in winter" (1986), "It snowed in the mountains" (1987) took place in his collections.

In Shukur Kholmirezayev's stories and stories, along with the unique romance of his youth and student years, the life of the simple, sincere people of Boysun, where the writer was born and raised, the changes in society and the spiritual world of the people are artistically interpreted. Literary experts say that the life of Boysun and the people of Boysun rose to the level of the main theme of Shukur Kholmirezayev's work, and became an important factor in the fact that the realistic image became the priority in the writer's work. As Shukur Kholmirezayev discovered the complex life processes in reality and the spiritual world of people consisting of conflicts, the romantic pathos in his early stories gave way to realism and created an opportunity for the writer to introduce elements of "brutal realism" into Uzbek literature. In his works created in the 80s and 90s, Shukur Kholmirezayev gave a deep artistic analysis of the society and people's life in that period.

During the years of independence, the writer rediscovered himself. The breath of freedom breaks the chains of the writer's thinking. Now he is overflowing and creates freely. We have inherited the precious works of this great writer who believed that literature was his destiny. His stories were collected in 3 volumes, his essays in 1 volume, short stories in 1 volume. This selection, consisting of 5 volumes in total, was published between 2005 and 2007. Shukur Kholmirezayev "Last Station" (1976), "Kil Bridge" (1984), "Passenger" (1987), "Olaboji" (1992), "Dinosaur" (Book 1, 1996) like his novels showed that the writer has become a master of prose. In Shukur Kholmirezayev's novels "Last Station", "Passenger" and "Olaboji" the shura society began to decay from the inside in the 70s and 80s through bright artistic images. The social issue raised in these novels found its new artistic interpretation in the writer's novel "Dinosaur". The story of the conflict in the life and spiritual world of a person who strongly believes that the Shura state is a people-friendly state, and that the internal and external

policies he conducted is a policy that serves the interests of the people and the country, is at the center of this novel.

The last novel of the writer is "Dinosaur". The author says: "The theory that the strong will win and the weak will be defeated is wrong!" If the strong had the ability to conquer, the dinosaur would have conquered first. No, he will die. The reason? It has been formed. Then: many brave men enter the field. They know their death. But there is no turning back for them. What about cowards? Those who got into their holes right then..." No matter how controversial such a view is, it is noticeable that the author took a unique way of reflecting the tragedy and suffering of the intellectuals in accepting the present day - the new era.

Shukur Kholmirzayev was one of the first writers to study the era of the Uzbek people's history, which was called the "printing movement". This topic was expressed in the writer's novel "Kil koprik" and "Black Belt" (1987). The tragedy of lost people is vividly embodied in their images. Based on Shukur Kholmirzayev's play, the play "Black belt" staged at the Youth Theater named after Abror Hidoyatov played an important role in the emergence of a new approach to the historical past in the young generation. Shukur Kholmirzayev's play "Banquet" dedicated to the tragic fate of Uzbek women during the Soviet era was also staged at the Youth Theater (1990). In the last years of Shukur Kholmirzayev's life Sh. Burkhanov, B. Zakirov, R. Choriyev, Shuhrat, O. Yakubov, O'. He wrote essays and literary-critical articles about such well-known figures of literature and art as Umarbekov, A. Oripov, M. Koshjanov.

Despite the fact that Shukur Kholmirzayev wrote a number of works in the novel genre and these works have a special place in the history of Uzbek novelists of this period, he is primarily a storyteller. In his stories, he continued the best traditions of Uzbek writers such as A. Qadiri, A. Qahhor, and enriched Uzbek storytelling with the artistic experiences of Russian and European writers. The best stories of Shukur Kholmirzayev are distinguished by the new and bright image of the hero, the originality of the composition, and the diversity of the language of the characters. While observing the creative workshop of the writer, we are convinced of how demanding he is of himself and the power of his talent. He rewrote a story 8 times until the literary work became a true work of art, aiming to present the reader with unique and original works. Throughout his life, the writer did not chase wealth and career. He lived a humble and simple life in the house of creativity in Dorman. His love for artistic words gave him strength. He enjoyed world prose and studied the unique styles of writers such as Hemingway, Jack London and Tagore. And without a doubt, he was able to create his own style - the style of Shukur Kholmirzayev. This style is national, pure, Uzbek! Shukur Kholmirzayev's prolific work was

highly appreciated, and in 1991, the writer was awarded the title of People's Writer of Uzbekistan, and in 1999, he was awarded the Order of Labor Fame. The writer who contributed noble works to world literature passed away in 2005.

REFERENCES:

1. Toshboyev O. Abadi, a contemporary. Gafur Ghulam NMIU, Tashkent. 2018
2. Sanjar Sadiq. History of new Uzbek literature. Teacher. NMIU. Tashkent. 2019
3. Shukur Kholmirezayev in memory of his contemporaries. Gafur Ghulam NMIU. Tashkent. 2018
4. Ulugmurodov D. Adiblar (Modern Tazkira). "Firdavs Shah" publishing house. Tashkent. 2021 year.